

This report summarises the deliverables to date (from August 2018 to August 2019) and provides key outcomes, findings and recommendations of EirWind – a MaREI Centre industry-led innovative and collaborative research project. It also presents the team's research publications and selected outreach, research and public engagement activities.

This project has received funding from the following industry partners: Brookfield Renewable Ireland, DP Energy Ireland, EDP Renewables, Electricity Supply Board, Enerco Energy, ENGIE, Equinor ASA, Simply Blue Energy, SSE Renewables, and Statkraft Ireland; and from Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) under Grant No 12/RC/2302 and University College Cork, Ireland.

Project start date: 01st August 2018

Duration: 2 years

Webpage: www.marei.ie/eirwind/

EirWind Mid-term Report

Co-designing opportunities
towards the development of Irish
offshore wind

EirWind Project Team,
MaREI, the SFI Centre for Energy, Climate
and Marine, Environmental Research
Institute, University College Cork
Cork, Ireland, October 2019

Disclaimer

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Attribution - Please cite the report as follows:

V. N. Dinh, V. Cummins, J. Murphy (editors) (2019). *Project mid-term report*. EirWind Project Deliverable D1.2 Report, MaREI Centre, ERI, University College Cork, Ireland. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3948230>

Document control:

Version	Date	Document History	Edited by	Reviewed by	Approved by
01	21/08/2019	Draft, sent out for Consortium meeting	Van Nguyen Dinh	Paul Leahy, Emma Critchley, Yvonne Cronin, Pedro Pereira	
02	22/08/2019	Minor edits: project description & Fig captions, added D6.2	Van Nguyen Dinh	Val Cummins	Val Cummins
03	30/08/2019	Updated DP Energy logo	Van Nguyen Dinh	Clodagh McGrath (DP Energy)	
04	08/10/2019	Update deliverable status, lists of publications, other research activities, and public engagement	Van Nguyen Dinh	Anne Marie O'Hagan, Paul Leahy, Jared Peters, Fiona Devoy McAuliffe, Yvonne Cronin, Emma Critchley, Jimmy Murphy, Val Cummins	Val Cummins, Jimmy Murphy

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1 Project General Information

1.1 Statement of Work

1.1.1 Project Description

EirWind is a MaREI Centre industry-led collaborative research project, proposed by Cummins et al. [1], [2], [3], and [4], co-designing the opportunity around the sustainable development of Ireland's marine resources, using offshore wind as the catalyst for innovation and impact. It is a collaborative project with ten industry partners to help accelerate opportunities towards the development of offshore wind in Ireland. The project involves the utilisation of Marine Spatial Planning concepts to address aspects such as consenting and policy/legislative frameworks; stakeholder engagement frameworks; data management frameworks; technical, environmental and societal constraints; and the production of development strategies for offshore wind energy case study zones. The deliverables will include strategy options for market, storage and infrastructure development, long-term GIS and data catalogue/repository for each of the study zones, and a blueprint for development for offshore wind, in approximately three hypothetical study zones, providing technical insights for developers and policy makers alike.

Objectives: The general objective is to provide data and information to facilitate the identification of potential zones for offshore wind farms, to enable decision-making. The specific objectives are to:

- Develop a data management framework, in the study of strategic areas for the development of offshore wind, off Ireland's east, south and west coasts (WP2).
- Review the challenges associated with consenting offshore wind projects, improve cost optimisation tools and cost reduction solutions, in order to develop an advanced approach to planning future development sites (WP3). Include a study on the potential for co-location of activities.
- Review stakeholder engagement, policy and legislative frameworks including community co-ownership, and previous practice, and, where relevant, suggest new and improved methods for planning of stakeholder management in the study area to identify issues and their relative importance at an early stage (WP4). Improve understanding of issues pertaining to impacts on fisheries and marine mammals.
- Provide data and information to help inform developers and policy makers about potential risks to seabirds to take into consideration for planning (WP4).
- Provide an overview of the status of the electricity and gas networks, relevant to the region, as well as development strategies for the distribution and storage of energy, including export market possibilities (WP5)
- Assess impacts from the development of renewable energies offshore in as much detail as possible, from a biological, environmental, infrastructural and sociological point of view. Cumulative and proximity-effects will be considered. Where possible, mitigations will be suggested (WP6).
- Make recommendations on optimised development strategies for selected case study zones.

Project Start Date/End Date: The project duration is two years. Start date: 1st August 2018 (Month 1).

1.1.2 Project Milestones (M), Deliverables (D), Timeline and Status:

Table 1. Leaders, description, timelines and status of EirWind milestones and deliverables

Work Package	Task Title/Leader(s)	Milestone/Deliverable	Deliverable Description	Status
1	Project management/ Dr V Cummins & Dr J Murphy	Month 1: M1.1	Kick off meeting.	Completed
		Month 24: D1.1	Monitor progress, tracking deliverables	In progress
		Months 4, 8: M1.1.1-M.1.1.2	Project consortium meetings (every approx. 3 months)	Completed
		Month 11: M1.2	Review & Revision of Progress & Work Plan	Completed
		Month 12: M1.1.3	Project consortium meeting.	Completed
		Month 12: D1.2	Interim MaREI project admin report	In progress
		Months 16, 20: M1.2.1-M.1.2.2	Project consortium meetings (every approx. 3 months)	To do
		Months 24: M1.3	Final project meeting	To do
		Month 24: D1.3	Final MaREI project admin report.	To do
2	Data management for site evaluation (D2.5 added as of 05 new partners)/ Prof. A Wheeler	Month 6: D2.1	Data Resources Assessment—Phase 1 (Data Requirements, Gap analysis and Strategic Plan)	Completed
		Month 8: D2.2	Field Measurement Plan 1	Completed
		Month 11: D2.3	Data Set Release 1 (Open GIS), in accordance with data standards, and as per the requirements of the industry partners.	Completed
		Month 11: M2.1	Review & Revision of Progress & Work Plan	Completed
		Month 12: M2.2	Interim Data Report	Completed
		Month 18: D2.4	Data Resources Assessment—Phase 2 report on 3-4 development zones	In progress
		Month 22: D2.5	Field Measurement Plan 2	To do
		Month 23: D2.6	Data Set Release 2 (Open GIS), in accordance with data standards, and as per the requirements of the industry partners.	To do
3	Development optimisation for Cost Reduction (D3.2, D3.4, D3.5 & D3.6 added as of 05 new partners) Revised milestones of M3.2, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4 as of staff changeover	Month 2: M3.1	First round of scenario building workshops (for each study site)	Completed
		Month 4: D3.1	Initial issues report on Offshore Wind farm Development in Ireland.	Completed
		Month 15: M3.2	Second round of scenario modelling consultations (for each study site).	In progress
		Month 11: M3.3	Review & Revision of Progress & Work Plan	Completed
		Month 15: D3.2	Modelling tool description (after completion of development) and application to various scenarios at generic site locations on east, south and west coasts.	In progress
		Month 19: D3.3	Report on optimization analysis in relation to zone development.	To do
		Month 24: D3.4	User friendly software decision support system for financial modelling	To do

	Dr J Murphy	Month 20: D3.5	Report on co-location with other sectors, building on the European Marina project report.	To do
		Month 23: D3.6	Report on cost reduction solutions.	To do
4	Governance/ Dr V Cummins (D4.3, 4.6, D4.9, M4.4, M4.5, D4.11 – 4.14 added as of 05 new partners) (M4.4, M4.5, , D4.11, D4.12, D4.13, D4.14 co-led by Dr Mark Jessop) Revised milestone of D4.5 as of the dynamic nature of the policy and legislative changes	Month 4: D4.1	Stakeholder map.	Completed
		Month 8: D4.2	Report – Recommendations for innovation and best practice in support of approaches to stakeholder engagement in the study areas.	Completed
		Month 9: D4.3	Comparative analysis of regulatory regime Ire/Scotland	Completed
		Month 10: D4.4	Stakeholder Perceptions Report 1	Completed
		Month 20: D4.5	Legal, policy and public participation review Report 1	In progress
		Month 10: M4.1	1 st report 1 of stakeholder engagement and perception studies	Completed
		Month 11: M4.2	Review & Revision of Progress & Work Plan.	Completed
		Month 16: D4.6	Interim report on models for community co-ownership (including best practice in terrestrial and international cases)	In progress
		Month 22: D4.7	Stakeholder Perceptions Report 2.	Doing
		Month 22: D4.8	Legal, policy and public participation review Report 2	To do
		Month 22: M4.3	2 nd report of stakeholder engagement and perception studies	To do
		Month 22: D4.9	Recommendations on community engagement (inc. co-ownership) for Ireland’s offshore wind resources, including Trust building with key stakeholders.	To do
		Month 23: D4.10	Socio-economic study	In progress
		Month 7: M4.4	Methodology outline and scenario identification on mitigation of impacts of offshore wind farms on seabirds	Completed
		Month 9: D4.11	Initial report on methodology for the assessment of seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland	Completed
		Month 12: D4.12	Initial results for the assessment of seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland	Completed
		Month 12: D4.13	Impacts from Offshore Wind Farms on Marine Mammals and Fish – A review of the current knowledge	Completed
Month 15: M4.5	Final outputs on seabird vulnerability mapping	In progress		
Month 17: D4.14	Final report on impacts of offshore wind farms on seabirds and marine mammals	To do		
5	Markets, infrastructures and economic benefits (D5.6, D5.7, D5.8, D5.9 added as of 05 new partners)/	Month 3: D5.1	Markets report-Identification of new and Future Markets	Completed
		Month 6: D5.2	Cost/Benefit and risk analysis report.	Completed
		Month 9: D5.3	Infrastructures and Storage Report 1	Completed
		Month 15: D5.4	System Services Report 1	In progress
		Month 10: D5.5	Demonstration Pilots design and recommendations 1	Completed
		Month 10: M5.1	Report delivery	Completed
		Month 11: M5.2	Review & Revision of Progress & Work Plan	Completed

Revised milestones as of late recruitment Dr P Leahy & Dr N Dinh	Month 17: D5.6	Projections for future levels of wind curtailment for market arrangements	To do
	Month 15: D5.7	Enhanced review of electrolyser and power-to-gas technologies with a focus on variable operation and system services	In progress
	Month 23: D5.8	Recommendation on role of government and funding mechanisms for infrastructure development	To do
	Month 17: D5.9	Report on the existing and developing interconnectors and their capacity strategies	To do
	Month 21: D5.10	Full Economic analyses.	To do
	Month 23: D5.11	Demonstration Pilots design and recommendations 2.	To do
	Month 23: M5.3	Final Report	To do
	Month 24: M5.4	Workshop	To do
6 Synthesis/ Dr V Cummins & Dr J Murphy	Month 2: D6.1	EirWind Outreach Plan	Completed
	Month 11: D6.2	Synthesis /Blueprint 1 for phased approach to sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland.	2 nd draft, updating
	Month 11: M6.3	Review & Revision of Progress & Work Plan	Completed
	Month 23: D6.4	Synthesis /Blueprint 2 for phased approach to sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland.	In progress
	Month 24: D6.5	Review and final report of EirWind Outreach and Impacts	To do

Note: The dissemination of deliverables in WP 1-6 will include publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences and be governed by the Publication Criteria in the Project Contractual Agreement.

1.2 Project Consortium

Research partner/host: MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, ERI, UCC, Ireland

Industry Partners: DP Energy Ireland, Equinor ASA, Enerco Energy, Statkraft Ireland, Brookfield Renewable Ireland, EDP Renewables, SSE Ireland, Simply Blue Energy, ENGIE, and Electricity Supply Board (ESB)

The EirWind's ten industry partners are an ideal mix of five multinational partners (from Canada, France, Norway, Spain and UK) and five partners from Ireland. These are a potential supply chain including environment, offshore wind developers, offshore engineering and technology, energy storage and grid integration.

Principal Investigators: Dr Valerie Cummins and Dr Jimmy Murphy

Project Manager: Dr Van Nguyen Dinh

1.2.1 Research Team

WP 2: Data management for site evaluation

- Prof. Andrew Wheeler (WP Leader)
- Dr Jared Peters

- Ross O'Connell (since September 2019)
- Tiny Remmers (up to July 2019)

WP 3: Development optimisation for Cost Reduction

- Dr Jimmy Murphy (WP Leader)
- Dr Fiona Devoy McAuliffe (Adjunct member¹)
- Dr Cian Desmond (Adjunct member¹)
- Prasad Gade (up to May 2019)
- Rachel Chester (up to December 2018)

WP4: Governance and Biological

- Dr Valerie Cummins (WP Leader)
- Dr Mark Jessop (WP Co-Leader, Biological)
- Dr Declan Jordan (WP Co-Leader, Socio and Spatial Economics)
- Yvonne Cronin
- Dr Sarah Kandrot
- Dr Mitra Kami Delivand
- Dr Emma Jane Critchley
- William Hunt (until July 2019)
- Dr Anne Marie O'Hagan (Adjunct member¹)
- Zoe O'Hanlon, Researcher (Adjunct member¹)
- Dr Ger Mullally (Adjunct member¹ – co-supervisor masters thesis Y Cronin)
- Dr Mike Fitzpatrick (Fisheries expert)

WP5: Markets, infrastructures and economic benefits

- Dr Paul Leahy (WP Leader)
- Dr Eamon McKeogh (Energy Market and Storage Technical specialist)
- Dr Van Nguyen Dinh (WP Co-Leader)
- Jochelle Laguipo
- Pedro Pereira

WP6: Synthesis

- Dr Valerie Cummins (WP Co-Leader)
- Dr Jimmy Murphy (WP Co-Leader)
- Dr Eamon McKeogh (Consultant)
- Dr Van Nguyen Dinh

¹ Adjunct member: UCC staff currently not funded by EirWind budget but is contributing or advising technically to the project deliverables.

1.2.2 Industry partner experts

In addition to providing direct cash to the project, the industry partners have contributed representatives with relevant expertise in multi-disciplines, as listed in **Table 2**, to interact with the EirWind research team in project meetings, material review, and provide practical and up-to-date feedback about the barriers and challenges. Such interaction and feedback are extremely beneficial for research activities and project human resource development.

Table 2. List of industry partners' experts contributed technically to EirWind project.

No	Partner name	Representatives & Expertise
1	DP Energy Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Development Manager (experience in offshore renewable energy development). • Consenting Manager (experience in marine energy EIAs and consenting processes). • Electrical development engineer
2	Equinor ASA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vice President, Director of Business Development • Principal Sustainability Engineer • Project leader, project management and control • Vice President, Offshore projects & operations (until May 2019) • Project Manager - Business Development (Until May 2019) • Leader, Project Management and Control, early phase development of offshore wind farms (until October 2018). • Advisor Business Development, New Energy Systems (Manager of Hywind project in Scotland – the world's first floating wind farm) (Pre-project development, until June 2018).
3	Enerco Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing Director • Finance Controller • Support Wind Asset Engineer (Until May 2019) • Offshore wind farm development and consenting (Until Jan 2019)
4	Brookfield Renewable Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Director HSS&E & Strategic Relationships, Europe, Europe. • Project Manager, Wind energy development • GIS Analyst
5	Statkraft Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEO (Formerly Power Projects Director & Chief Development Officer), Experience in wind farm development, interconnectors. • Senior Project Manager • Project Manager (April – August 2019) • GIS Manager Ireland (until April 2019)
6	EDP Renewables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Offshore Wind Manager, since July 2019 • Project Consent Manager • International Offshore Wind Manager, Experience in offshore wind development, Until July 2019
7	SSE Ireland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Manager, Offshore Development • Director of Special Projects (Until March 2019)

8	Simply Blue Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEO and Director, Governance, Business development. • Senior Environmental Consultant
9	ENGIE Lab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Senior Research Engineer, Experience in Hydrogen, power to gas, renewable energy integration and processes • Research Engineer, Hydrogen Lab - CRIGEN
10	Electricity Supply Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offshore Wind Development Manager, ESB Asset Dev • Manager, Innovation and R&D Demonstration, ESB Generation and Trading

1.3 Technical Advisory Group

The EirWind Advisory Group (EAG) includes representatives from:

- Department of Housing, Planning and Local Government (DHPLG)
- Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI)
- Marine Institute
- Geological Survey of Ireland (GSI)
- Marine Renewable Industry Association (MRIA)
- Irish Maritime Development Office (IMDO)
- Enterprise Ireland (Since January 2019)
- Commissioners of Irish Lights (since August 2019)

1.4 Summary of project meetings, workshops and events

As designed, the project has organised regular meetings as summarised in **Table 3** with high level interaction between the researchers and industry partners as well as input from the members of the Technical Advisory Group. These meetings have acted as a ‘validation’ mechanism to ensure the project work is kept industry relevant. The EirWind industry partners and the research team have had several opportunities to participate in events and consultations, aimed at influencing the development of offshore wind in Ireland as in **Table 3**. They are also beneficial from the implementation of the communications and dissemination strategy.

Table 3. Project meetings, workshop and events organised by the EirWind research team for industry experts – technical advisors – research team interactions

No	Time & Venue	No/mix of participants	Description & Outcome
1	2018, February 08, Cork	27, from 7 industry partners, technical advisors, research	Pre-project meeting. Discussions about the technical action plans of each work package, updates from industry partners, advisors and research team
2	2018, May 25, Dublin	28, from 8 industry partners, technical advisors & research	Pre-project meeting. Further discussions about technical action plans of each work package; updates from industry partners, advisors and research team

3	2018, August 30, Cork	34, from 10 industry partners, research and technical advisors (PM)	Project Consortium Meeting. Updates from advisors and industry; finalised full scope of work proposed by research team [3] [4] w.r.t. new industry partners
4	2018, August - October	3-5, from WP3 & 4 and representatives of each industry partner.	Various interviews with representatives of each industry partner by WP3 and WP4 for input to Scenario Building and Stakeholder engagement
5	2018, October 22, Cork	20, from industry partners and research team	WP3 Scenario Building Workshop. Discussions about the finalised base case scenarios and optimisation strategies that would be used to identify areas of potential cost reduction (M3.1 and D3.1)
6	2018, November 29 (9:00 – 13:00 hrs), Cork	30, from 10 industry partners and research team	Project Consortium Meeting. Reviewed progress of D2.1, D2.3, D3.1, D4.1 and report of D5.1. Discussion about further technical action plan.
7	2018, November 29 (14:00 – 17:30 hrs), Cork	36, from 10 industry partners, research and technical advisors	Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) Workshop (organised by EirWind). EirWind brief updates; Updates on MSP from advisors and researchers; Group discussions; Finalised response .
7	2019, January 31 (9 – 13:00 hrs) Dublin	30, from industry partners and research team	Project Consortium Meeting. Reviewed progress/delivery of D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D3.1, D3.2, D4.1, D4.2, D4.6, D4.10 and D4.11. Discussions about further technical action plan.
8	2019, January 31 (14 – 17:30 hrs), Dublin	40, from industry partners, research team, advisors, invited speakers and EirGrid	Grid-Marine Spatial Planning Workshop (organised by Eirwind). EirWind brief updates; Curtailment analysis presentation from Mullan Grid & discussion; Group discussions; a report published online.
9	2019, February 01, Dublin	200+ attendees, most of EirWind industry partners	National Forum organised by Marine Renewable Energy Industry (MRIA). Dr Cummins (EirWind Co-PI) and Ms O’Hanlon gave two invited presentations. Industry partners – DCCA Minister meeting.
10	2019, May 02, Cork	35, from industry partners & research team	Project Consortium Meeting. Reviewed progress/delivery of D2.2, D2.3, D4.3, D4.4, D4.6, D4.10, D4.11, D4.12, D4.13 and D5.2. Discussions about further technical action plan.
11	2019, June 10, Cork (17:000 – 21:00 hrs), after the Ocean Wealth Summit.	100+, from government agencies, UCC, MaREI Centre, extended industry and research team	MaREI EirWind networking event (organised by EirWind team and funded by the MaREI Centre). Opening speech by Vice Admiral Mark Mellett, participation from Mr Simon Coveney – Tánaiste and the Norwegian Ambassador to Ireland. Demonstration of MaREI Centre reports, and EirWind public reports on offshore wind farm issues ; comparison of Scotland and Ireland ; and policy briefs on data , seabird vulnerability , and hydrogen .
12	2019, August 27, Cork	40, from industry partners, research team, and technical advisors.	Project Consortium Meeting. Reviewed the progress of work over the last 12 months including D2.2, D2.3, D4.3, D4.4, D4.6, D4.10-4.13, D5.2, D5.3 and D5.5; Obtained feedback and input from the technical Advisory Group; Refined the next six month work plan, including the synthesis aspects; Updates and group discussion on development scenarios of offshore wind in Ireland.

2 Work Package 2: Data management for site evaluation

2.1 Data Resources Assessment—Phase 1 (Deliverable D2.1)

Prepared by: Jared Peters

Reviewed by: Valerie Cummins, Andrew Wheeler, Tiny Remmers and Industry partners

Executive Summary:

This report assesses the quality and availability of data resources applicable to offshore wind farm development on the continental shelf of Ireland. Research was guided by five aims:

- Establish data standards
- Outline data requirements
- Describe available data
- Reveal data gaps
- Use data assessments to strategize future work

To address these objectives systematically, a meta-analysis of peer-reviewed offshore wind farm site analyses was performed. This analysis revealed standards in the types of variables, methods, and data resolutions used in such analyses. This standard was used to guide the data assessment for development of Ireland's offshore wind-energy industry. Wind data were found to be the most commonly used variables in the reviewed literature, followed by water depth and protected areas. Conversely, geological characteristics and shipwreck locations were the least examined variables. Methodological commonalities from the literature review also suggest a multi-phase assessment structure for site assessments. Following this standard, variables are organised into two distinct groups: utilization restrictions (i.e. exclusion-zone variables) and de-risking factors (i.e. suitability variables). Similarly, a format for future analysis is suggested that uses these variables in two phases of assessment: an initial, low-resolution examination, followed by more focused examinations of specific regions.

A list of required data was compiled from the meta-analysis results, which consists of 22 variables. The availability and quality of each variable's data are described as part of a comprehensive examination of the available data sources. In addition to revealing potential data sources, this examination elucidates the available resolutions, and file types of existing data.

Following this assessment, a comparative examination of the required- and available-data was performed. This assessment revealed four types of data gaps and shortfalls: (1) omitted data; (2) unavailable data; (3) data with inadequate resolution; and (4) data with inappropriate file types. Four geological variables have data gaps arising from omissions:

- Surface sediment lithology
- Depth to bedrock
- Stratigraphy

- Height-appropriate visual impact

Two variables have data gaps arising from availability issues:

- Shipping
- Seabed morphology and slope

Eight variables have inadequate data resolutions:

- Water depth
- Wind velocity
- Wave height (Hs)
- Ocean currents
- Seabed morphology and slope
- Surface sediment lithology
- Depth to bedrock
- Stratigraphy

Ten variables have inappropriate file types:

- Water depth
- Utilities
- Shipping
- Wave height (Hs)
- Ocean currents
- Surface sediment lithology
- Depth to bedrock
- Stratigraphy
- Distance to ports
- Distance to grid connections

Following these assessments, ongoing work was summarised, and work for the next six months was strategized. Ongoing work includes processing and analyses of data collected during the CV18034 research cruise conducted in October 2018. These analyses include geomorphic examinations of new multibeam bathymetric data and sedimentary examinations of new sediment-grab and sediment-core samples. GIS analyses and data processing are also underway, which aim to develop novel data sources that may streamline future site assessments. Future work will also include weighting the relative importance of data variables and planning and implementation of future research cruises for which funding has already been obtained.

Policy Brief URL: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Policy-Brief---Data-for-Offshore-Wind-in-Ireland.pdf>

2.2 Field Measurement Plan 1 (Deliverable D2.2)

Prepared by: Jared Peters

Reviewed by: Nguyen Dinh, Andrew Wheeler and Industry partners

Executive Summary:

This report establishes a strategy for collecting new data to improve Irish Offshore Wind Energy (OWE) assessments. It incorporates insights from experts in various academic and industrial fields. In this capacity, it does not entirely replace the research plan and work schedules being written for upcoming research cruises, but incorporates parts of those plans and helps inform upcoming expeditions to ensure compatibility with EirWind goals. Thus, descriptions of OWE data collection methods and how those methods have been used in planning upcoming research cruises are provided. This helps align future research to EirWind's goals.

In reviewing the available data required for planning a successful research cruise, several EirWind reports were consulted, indicating that the EirWind project is producing deliverables that are useful to offshore data collection efforts that target OWE variables. With the help of these reports, care was taken to minimize any unnecessary duplication of existing (and accessible) data during future offshore data collection efforts. This also maximises the capacity for data standardization. This report also uses new oceanographic and geologic data collected by the EirWind project (during research cruise CV18034) to improve future data collection efforts for Irish OWE developments.

Through these data reviews, a general strategy for selecting data collection sites for OWE development has been described. This strategy has been employed for planning the upcoming EirWind research cruise (CV19023), which is also described in sufficient detail to illustrate the logic of the research site selection methodology.

Research will be conducted during the upcoming cruise from the RV Celtic Voyager. A science crew will consist largely of experienced research assistants and will be led by an EirWind WP2 researcher. Research will focus on acquiring two types of data: oceanographic and geologic. Oceanographic data will be collected using a multi-beam echo sounder system and by deploying a series of acoustic Doppler current profiler and wave gauge buoys. Geologic data will be collected using various sediment sampling techniques and sub-bottom geophysics. The CV19023 research cruise will last for seven days (16/09/2019 – 22/09/2019). As depicted in the figure below, most of the operational time is required for transit, while oceanographic and sedimentologic data collection efforts are allocated roughly equal time.

Future applications for any data collected on upcoming cruises has also been strategized. These strategies include data gap reductions and advanced GIS model constructions and calibrations. Lastly, this report discusses the role of potential new data generated by future offshore research (e.g. CV19023) in the context of the overarching goals and workflow of the EirWind project. This context suggests that the ongoing efforts of EirWind's WP2 are likely to help progress OWE development through data standardisations and methodological advances.

Figure 2-1: Chart of time budgets for operations during the upcoming CV19023 research cruise

2.3 Data set release 1 (Deliverable D2.3)

Prepared by: Tiny Remmers

Reviewed by: Jared Peters, Nguyen Dinh, Valerie Cummins, Andrew Wheeler and Industry partners

Executive Summary:

The primary purpose of this report is to deliver new datasets to the EirWind Consortium. These datasets were created to fill the gaps identified by previous assessments of the existing data and have been developed on a broad, nation-wide level to enable integration into spatial Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) models. This report presents geographic information system (GIS) layers and models developed for improved data management and site evaluation for Irish offshore wind energy production. It consists of three primary elements:

- An overview of the 'Opportunity and Constraint Model' (OCM);
- A description of new data produced to improve the data gaps in the MCDA;
- A data repository which includes all the data that has been assessed and integrated into the GIS model.

The model OCM overview consists of brief definition of the MCDA techniques being employed and the advantages that this method provides. There is also a description of how the model is set up in ArcGIS using the ESRI 'Model Builder' tool. The workflow for the OCM development is documented in detail to enable reproducibility and customisation. Finally, these developments are discussed, highlighting the need for parameter weighting and the potential applicability of the model output.

The new data created for the EirWind model includes: an offshore Wind and Wave Analysis; three Distance-Cost Analyses; and a Visual Assessment Analysis. The methodology developed for each analysis is presented with the aim of maximising transferability with other datasets that may be used by the EirWind industry partners' GIS teams. The data integrated in the analyses are catalogued and presented as figures to enable visual assessments and improved conceptualisation of the methods employed and potential analytical applications. Limitations and uncertainties are also discussed, and alternative data sources are provided.

The data repository contains essential metadata for each layer, including: the datum's source; update(s); spatial resolution; coordinate system; metadata URL; and a short description. It is a searchable database where the data are classified by model categories. This has the advantage of identifying which datum may become problematic following model updates or customisation of any particular parameter. Thus, it is essential that the database is kept up to date to assure the most accurate MCDA output.

Future work and potential sources of additional data are also discussed. Primary foci for future work include: incorporating updated seabird and cetacean data into the MCDA; filling geological data gaps and incorporating geologic data into the MCDA; obtaining data on vessel positions and densities and incorporating these into the MCDA; maintaining the GIS database; and organising a collaborative effort across the EirWind consortium to assign weights (i.e. relative importance) to the model parameters. These goals can likely be met using additional data from: ongoing research (e.g. the OBSERVE project); 2017 Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) data; EMODnet European Union (EU) vessel density map; and continued data collection efforts by EirWind's Work Package 2, which will generate improved geological data.

3 Work Package 3: Development optimisation for Cost Reduction

3.1 Initial Issues in the Development of Offshore Wind in Ireland (Deliverable D3.1)

Prepared by: Rachel Chester

Reviewed by: Jimmy Murphy, Nguyen Dinh and Industry partners

Executive Summary:

This document highlights a number of key issues that face Ireland as it moves towards large scale offshore wind farm development. It provides an overview of challenges and provides recommendations on potential future strategies for Ireland. The report focuses on *Environmental Conditions*, *Irish Ports* and *Supply Chain and Expertise*. It addresses specific issues relevant to Ireland across the lifecycle process of an offshore wind farm including: installation; operation and maintenance; and decommissioning.

The *Environmental Conditions* section points to the energetic nature of Irelands offshore waters and the opportunities and challenges that presents. The *Ports* section highlights the current lack of port capacity in Ireland particularly for installation purposes and that initial offshore wind farms in Ireland are likely to be developed from non-Irish ports. The *Supply Chain and Expertise* section indicates that Ireland currently has a limited but very expert supply chain that has the potential for significant growth as the industry develops.

An overall recommendation is that stronger commitment from government is necessary to enable the development of a pipeline of projects, prove bankability and instil confidence into the industry such that to encourage private investment.

Full report URL: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Deliverable-D3.1-Initial-Issues-in-the-Development-of-Offshore-Wind-in-Ireland.pdf>

3.2 Scenario building workshops (Milestones M3.1 and M3.2)

Prepared by: Fiona Devoy McAuliffe

Reviewed by: Jimmy Murphy

Executive Summary:

WP 3 also conducted an industry consultation workshop on 22nd October 2018 at the MaREI Centre, Ringaskiddy, Co. Cork. The purpose was to finalise three generic Offshore Wind Farm scenarios on the East, South and West coasts of Ireland. It is important to note that these scenarios are intended to be representative of current and future potential OWFs given the general characteristics and resource available off the Irish coast. They are not based on any current or proposed wind farms off the Irish coast. In addition to each base case, industry identified associated optimisation scenarios looking at novel strategies and technologies that could provide cost reductions. These were ranked in order of priority/interest to the industry.

Each scenario will be modelled using a financial model comprising detailed discrete-event simulation tools for all three lifecycle phases (installation, operation and maintenance, and decommissioning). These utilise a Monte-Carlo simulation methodology to consider key uncertainties including reliability and weather conditions.

In addition to the workshop, WP 3 has contacted industry partners to help determine realistic inputs for the model. Once full scenarios have been documented, we will revert again to industry partners to validate the details prior to running each base case simulation.

4 Work Package 4: Governance and biological

4.1 Stakeholder Issues and Mapping (Deliverable D4.1)

Prepared by: Yvonne Cronin

Reviewed by: Valerie Cummins and Industry partners

Executive Summary

Stakeholder mapping evolves throughout project development. For our purposes, stakeholders were initially identified at the outset of the project, but this is an ongoing and iterative process. Key contacts were identified at a national level, and in some instances, at more regional and local scales. The methodology for analysing stakeholder perceptions to offshore wind in Germany used by Schmidt (2017) was adapted here. This document builds on the Stakeholder Directory produced by EirWind in November 2018. This document contains a directory of stakeholders specific to the Irish Sea, the Celtic Sea and the West Coast of Ireland zones as identified by WP3.

This document reports on findings of semi-structured interviews which took place between August and October 2018, (either face to face or by phone) with industry partners involved with EirWind, to identify areas of concern for potential offshore wind energy developers entering the Irish market. The interviews explored previous experience of stakeholder engagement (in Ireland or abroad), and established open-ended discussion on the research goals for the governance work package. Results were collated and presented anonymously.

Although the geographic focus of the EirWind Project is on the Republic of Ireland, because of its significance as a port for projects being developed in the Irish Sea, Belfast was also included in this report.

Seven primary stakeholder cohorts were identified as primary interest groups by the EirWind industry partners: i). Government – national through to local; ii). Supply chain – including port authorities; iii). Vested interest groups – e.g. fisheries; iv). General public; v). Print media – both traditional print and social media; vi). Political representatives – from national TDs to local level councillors; and vii). Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

Eleven main areas of concern with regard to governance were also identified, as the need to:

- i. Achieve greater clarity on the planning and consenting process.
- ii. Minimise issues around visual impact.
- iii. Address potential conflicts with fisheries, shipping and other vested interests.
- iv. Develop a coherent message from the sector about job creation, energy security, climate change, avoiding fines and blue growth.
- v. Explore options for co-location with different user groups.
- vi. Positively influence public perception, especially among the younger generations.
- vii. Encourage investment by government in critical enabling infrastructure including ports and grid.

- viii. Engage with public representatives to ensure a greater number of champions for offshore wind development in coastal communities going forward.
- ix. Deal more proactively with traditional print media, as well as social.
- x. Be aware of NGO perspectives.
- xi. Ensure research outputs are policy relevant.

These concerns, coupled with the stakeholder mapping exercise have led to the following recommendations for the governance work package:

- Legislative and policy analysis to be conducted to give clear guidance on the current and potential future systems for effective decision making.
- A measure of the socio economic impact for offshore wind to be prioritised.
- A national survey to be conducted to explore the public perception of offshore wind energy development in the seas around Ireland.
- A process to be initiated to improve understanding of how to achieve co-existence between specific marine users, to avoid use conflict in future offshore development.
- All of the above work stream should be synthesised into the design of campaign for promoting offshore wind.

4.2 Recommended Innovation & Best Practice Stakeholder Engagement (Deliverable D4.2)

Prepared by: Yvonne Cronin

Reviewed by: Valerie Cummins and Gerard Mullally

Executive Summary

The objective of this report is to inform about the existing research methodologies available for measuring stakeholder perception of renewable development, for the EirWind team to glean an understanding of stakeholder perceptions of offshore wind development scenarios. The role that stakeholder perception plays in the success or failure of renewable energy developments, and more specifically wind energy developments, is reported on. This review also reports on what is considered best practice for stakeholder engagement from both an international and, more specifically, an Irish context.

Stakeholder identification, analysis and mapping are essential elements which must be considered in order to ensure effective stakeholder engagement with respect to renewable energy development. Environmental development has far reaching effects on many different sections of society; practically, economically and emotionally. This ‘wicked’ problem is such that it is impossible to please all of the people all of the time and hence a best solution must be attained.

A plethora of techniques exist for identification, analysis, engagement and participation, together with countless reasons for objections against, and arguments for, the development of sustainable energy projects. Understanding what influences public perception is key to learning what triggers can be used in order to change public perception and behaviour. Effective stakeholder participation and engagement must include timely access to clear and relevant information, highly skilled facilitation and trusted intermediaries. Factors which can enhance relationships between stakeholders and developers, and hence aid acceptance of any potential development, include community benefits, two-way deliberative learning and transparency and fairness of process. Specific participation techniques will each have different outcomes and relevance to each group involved, but common to all techniques is the importance of trust and fairness in process.

The most important aspects of best practice for stakeholder participation are reported on with a comprehensive list of participatory methods being collated from current research. Examples of success and failures of stakeholder participation and engagement are drawn on to examine Ireland’s track record with renewable energy development. This paper examines the changing rationales and philosophies behind the varying levels of stakeholder engagement.

The report concludes that the EirWind project is in a position to learn from countries which are the forerunners in offshore renewable energy development. We can look to Germany and the U.K. who have made the greatest advances in the area of offshore renewable energy development, and learn from their experience, in order to develop our industry with a social licence to operate. This, together with the experience and expertise of the EirWind consortium, provides a template for best practice, described herein.

4.3 Regulatory Report – A Comparative Insight of Irish and Scottish Regulatory Frameworks for Offshore Wind Energy – An Expert Perspective (Deliverable D4.3)

Prepared by: Zoe O Hanlon and Valerie Cummins

Reviewed by: Anne Marie O’Hagan, Jimmy Murphy

Executive Summary

Sources of marine renewable energy, are of significant importance in achieving energy efficiency and transitions to sustainability. Of these marine innovations, offshore wind energy is growing at unprecedented levels, driven by technological maturity, cost reduction and political will. Ireland is significantly behind on European Union decarbonisation objectives, with a paucity of offshore wind development in Irish waters. Occupying a vast marine resource, Ireland has the potential to tap into this growing global marine market and set the trajectory toward sustainability. This analytical policy research investigates the key enablers and constraints to achieving that growth, using Scotland as a jurisdiction for comparative analysis. Scotland was chosen due to its advances in the deployment of floating offshore structures and the operation of Marine Scotland as a ‘one-stop-shop’ for project consenting. Using Scotland for comparison provides critical insight into experiences learned in an international context and how these may be applied to Ireland. The research utilises a qualitative method through 24 semi-structured interviews with experts selected from industry and policy.

Enablers of offshore wind in Ireland were identified as opportunities to be addressed in the enactment and implementation of the Maritime Area and Foreshore (Amendment) Bill; and the development of a policy statement specific to offshore wind, to accelerate sector development. Key constraints identified included a lack of government commitment and appropriate legislative instruments, inefficient policy support and issues with fragmentation across various government departments.

Enablers of offshore wind in Scotland were noted as government commitment, clear policy support and the Contracts for Difference (CfD)² electricity price support mechanism. The importance of transitional based skills from the oil and gas industry was recognised as aiding sector progression. The importance of Scotland’s ‘one-stop-shop’ consenting process was also discussed, and the implementation of technology specific auctions to allow development of offshore wind was deemed favourable. Key constraints identified for Scotland related to the future political stability of the sector in light of devolved UK government functions; delays caused by lack of knowledge of environmental impacts, and the current political climate surrounding Brexit.

The research notes four recommendations for progressing the Irish offshore wind sector, which include: - i). a government policy statement on offshore wind, ii). enactment of foreshore legislation to enable project development, iii). increased integration and resourcing across government departments, and iv). increased capacity building (knowledge generation and engagement of stakeholders).

Full report URL: <https://www.mare.i.e/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Deliverable-D4.3-Regulatory-Report—A-Comparative-Insight-of-Irish-and-Scottish-Regulatory-Frameworks-for-Offshore-Wind-Energy—An-Expert-Perspective.pdf>

² See <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/contracts-for-difference/contract-for-difference>

4.4 Stakeholder Perceptions Report - Part 1 (Deliverable D4.4)

Prepared by: Yvonne Cronin

Reviewed by: Valerie Cummins

Executive Summary

In order to realise a carbon free economy it is necessary for society to embrace developing technologies, not only theoretically but practically, both on a global and local level (Dwyer and Bidwell, 2019)¹. Until recently, Ireland has developed terrestrial wind farms without significant opposition (O'Connor, 2018)³. With increasing pressure to install more onshore wind farms (Lange et al., 2018)⁴, and to bring wind farms offshore, it was necessary to conduct a national study of public perception of offshore wind farms in Ireland. With only one offshore wind farm currently in Ireland, national studies investigating the Irish attitude to offshore wind farms are lacking. This report is an introduction to the methodologies, which have been designed in order to undertake national studies of public perception. This document provides information from case studies to inform questionnaire design, sampling strategy and a pilot study. The report led to the delivery of a survey of public perception towards offshore wind farms, undertaken in May and June 2019. The online questionnaire can be viewed by clicking on the following link or copying it to your browser:

<https://www.sphinxonline.com/SurveyServer/s/INTERACTIONS2/MareOffshoreWind/webform.htm>

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying an online questionnaire. The title is "We would like to know your thoughts on your experience of OFFSHORE wind farms". The questions and options are as follows:

- How many times a year do you visit the coast?
 Every day Once or twice a week Once or twice a month Once or twice every six months Ten times a year Never
- What activities do you take part in when at the coast?
Please choose as many as you like
 Beach walking Sailing Kite Surfing Deep Sea Angling Other, specify:
 Coastal walking Surfing Diving Snorkelling
 Swimming Kayaking Fishing None of these
- Have you ever seen an OFFSHORE wind farm? Yes No Don't know
- Can you see the coast from your house? Yes No Don't know
- Have you ever visited the coast to see an OFFSHORE wind farm? Yes No Don't know
- Have you ever avoided visiting the coast because of the presence of an OFFSHORE wind farm? Yes No Don't know

Navigation buttons: Previous, Next, and a progress indicator.

Figure 4-1: A screenshot of the online questionnaire

A screenshot of the online questionnaire is shown in [Figure 4-1](#). This generated data from over 1,000 participants. The review of the dataset will lead to Stakeholders Perception Report – Part 2.

¹Dwyer, J., Bidwell, D., 2019. Chains of trust: Energy justice, public engagement, and the first offshore wind farm in the United States. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 47, 166–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.08.019>

³ O'Connor, M.M., 2018. Social acceptability of wind farm development – a judicial eye at the centre of the perfect storm (Part 1 of 2). *Irish Planning and Environmental Law Journal* 25(1), 4-13

⁴ Lange, M., O'Hagan, A.M., Devoy, R.R.N., Le Tissier, M., Cummins, V., 2018. Governance barriers to sustainable energy transitions – Assessing Ireland's capacity towards marine energy futures. *Energy Policy* 113, 623–632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.11.020>

4.5 Models for community co-ownership (including best practice in terrestrial and international cases) (Ongoing Deliverable D4.6) and Recommendations on community engagement (including co-ownership) for Ireland's offshore wind resources, including trust building with key stakeholders (Ongoing Deliverable D4.9).

Prepared by: Mitra Kami Delivand

Reviewed by: Valerie Cummins

Overview note:

In the High Level Design (HLD) for the new Renewable Electricity Support Scheme (RESS) for Ireland, pathways for increased community participation will be a cornerstone of the new scheme, delivering on Energy White Paper commitments. Policy options will be implemented to support community-led projects and other measures to increase community participation. The local community perception of renewable energy benefits varies throughout the development stages notably during planning, consenting, construction and operation. The existing literature highlights the opportunities and challenges of community benefit schemes from indigenous power generation in several countries. It outlines the challenges of specifying who the relevant local community is, what form of community benefits would yield desirable opportunities, and why institutionalised guidance would provide greater clarity and give developers greater confidence to discuss the community benefits package in the early planning stages. In the first step, the objective of this study is to discuss community benefit schemes including co-ownership models for inshore and offshore energy cases. In the second step, the research studies the co-existence practices of sea users, trust building with relevant key stakeholders and the challenging nature of community benefits from offshore wind power development in Ireland. A series of semi-structured interviews is conducted involving the EirWind project industrial partners, several offshore wind developers outside the project, a number of fishers (or fisheries associations) in different regions of Ireland (the East, South, West and North) and some informal interviews with external experts. A mixed method approach is used to analyse the data. Within a common deductive thematic framework, data is categorized into appropriate codes using NVivo Plus Software. In an integrated inductive approach, the ideas from the open questions and new ideas from the deductive approach will be further analysed to capture an in-depth nature of qualitative data. In both coding system approaches, relevant examples in the data of each category will be provided and important ideas from the interviewees will be listed. In addition, a quantitative Analytical Hierarchy Process is applied to explore the subjective prioritization of community benefit options by the interviewees. The study will inform the concerns and interests of fishers which may contribute to improve a fair co-existence practice between offshore wind developers and fishers in Ireland.

4.6 Regional socioeconomic benefits and employment potential in the Irish offshore wind sector (Ongoing Deliverable D4.10)

Prepared by: Sarah Kandrot

Reviewed by: Valerie Cummins, Declan Jordan

Overview note:

The large-scale deployment of offshore wind projects off the coast of Ireland has the potential to have a significant impact on the Irish economy and coastal communities from which installation and operations and maintenance (O&M) activities are carried out. Increased employment opportunities, particularly in economically depressed rural areas, can stimulate regional economies and have a positive social impact on coastal communities, especially where newly created jobs are permanent, stable and well-paid. Such employment is not only created by individual projects, but also within the offshore wind sector supply chain in areas such as marine engineering and construction, environmental consulting, and equipment manufacture. The potential employment impacts of supply chain development of the offshore wind sector in Ireland has not yet been fully explored. Some studies have attempted to quantify employment potential in renewable energy technologies, although none has focussed explicitly on offshore wind. The aim of this research is to quantify the value and employment impacts of such developments using a supply chain approach. Although the supply chain for Ireland is not yet well developed, Ireland already has strong capabilities in a variety of sub-elements across the offshore wind lifecycle, such as marine consultancy, offshore surveying, and data analytics. For this research, a supply chain model based on expenditure and annual wages is under development to explore future employment potential for a range of scenarios. A novel feature of this model is that it will allow us to map the potential geographical distribution of employment at a sub-national level, given the current level of planned development. This information will be used to inform professional training requirements to stimulate future development of the Irish offshore wind industry.

4.7 Initial report on methodology for the assessment of seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland (Deliverable D4.11)

Prepared by: Emma Critchley

Reviewed by: Mark Jessopp, Valerie Cummins

Executive Summary:

Understanding the potential risks to seabirds is an essential component of any offshore wind farm development, yet assessments can often be challenging when large areas are involved. Vulnerability indices are a practical method for calculating both individual risk and population level vulnerability for multiple species at a time, without the need for specific site information. When applied to species distribution maps these indices can provide spatial information about potential areas where high concentrations of vulnerable species may occur.

Offshore wind vulnerability indices for seabirds have been developed as a practical method for assessing impacts in countries with extensive offshore wind developments, such as Germany and the UK. The biological component of EirWind Work Package 4 will develop a set of vulnerability indices to inform the assessment of the potential vulnerability of seabirds to offshore wind farms specifically in Irish waters. This analysis will make use of the most recent information on seabird behaviour in relation to offshore wind infrastructure, species' conservation status, and the likely scenarios of the development of offshore wind in Irish waters. In particular, it will account for the larger 12 MW turbines which will be deployed in the future, providing a significant advance on previous indices.

A Collision Vulnerability Index will assess the population level vulnerability to potential collisions with offshore wind turbines for all seabird species in Ireland. A separate Displacement Vulnerability index will assess the population level vulnerability to displacement from important habitats due to the siting of offshore wind developments.

These indices will be applied to the most up to date distribution data for seabirds in Irish waters to generate vulnerability maps. Maps will cover the entire Irish EEZ, but will also be available at a finer scale for specific regions such as the Irish sea. This data and information will help to inform developers and policy makers about risk in relation to proposed siting of developments and identifying areas where more detailed surveys may need to be conducted in consideration of planning.

4.8 Initial results for the assessment of seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland (Deliverable D4.12)

Prepared by: Emma Critchley

Reviewed by: Mark Jessopp, Valerie Cummins

Executive Summary:

Seabirds spend a significant portion of their time at sea, where they are vulnerable to impacts from marine energy infrastructure such as offshore wind farms. Therefore, it is essential that the potential risks to seabird populations, either through collision with turbines or displacement from important foraging areas, are assessed prior to development.

Very little is known about the vulnerability of seabirds to offshore wind farms in Irish waters. Seabird vulnerability indices have been developed as part of the biological component of EirWind Work Package 4 through updating previously published indices in an Irish context, incorporating new data, and accounting for advances in turbine technology. Two Collision Vulnerability Indices were calculated, one accounting for a turbine sweep zone starting at 20 m above sea level, and one accounting for a turbine sweep zone starting at 40 m above sea level.

Collision vulnerability was generally lower for all species in the 40 m index compared to the 20 m index, indicating that if larger turbines are installed in Irish waters overall collision risk could be lower than previously expected. A separate Displacement Vulnerability Index (DVI) was produced to assess population level vulnerability to displacement from important habitats due to the siting of offshore wind developments. Generally, species with a high DVI score (e.g. divers and auks) had low CVI scores. Conversely, shearwaters and storm petrels had the lowest DVI scores but high CVI scores.

All vulnerability index scores were applied to seabird distributions in the Irish Sea. These show a distinction between the areas of highest vulnerability for collision susceptible species and displacement susceptible species, particularly in the summer. Therefore, species and risk factors will vary by site and season. The Vulnerability scores (CVI and DVI) will be applied to seabird distribution data covering the entire Irish EEZ in Deliverable D4.14 due at the end of December.

4.9 Impacts from Offshore Wind Farms on Marine Mammals and Fish – A review of the current knowledge (Deliverable D4.13)

Prepared by: William Hunt

Reviewed by: Emma Critchley, Mark Jessopp, Valerie Cummins and Industry partners.

Executive Summary:

This report addresses the need for a robust overview of the science, in order to understand current knowledge of the impacts of offshore wind development, as the sector develops in Ireland. As such, the report summarises an extensive literature review of the known impacts from construction and operation of offshore wind farms (OWFs) on marine mammals and fish/shellfish. In addition, an overview of the currently available mitigation methods has been provided. The chief potential stressors of marine life from offshore wind farms have been identified as 1) noise, 2) built structures, 3) vessel activity, and 4) cables, comprising both power cables and mooring lines.

Noise is a known stressor of both marine mammals and fish and is currently the most significant stressor from OWFs. Impacts include acoustic trauma, hearing impairments, masking of biologically important acoustic signals, behavioural changes, and physiological stress. How these impacts manifest varies between fish and marine mammals, will often vary between species within these groups, and between size/age of individuals within a single species. Marine mammals detect noise through sound pressure alone, crustaceans likely detect noise solely through particle motion, fish may use either one or both. Recently revised thresholds for marine mammals in the literature may influence changes in Irish guidelines for permitted anthropogenic noise emission levels. Guidelines for thresholds for fish could also be adopted from the available literature.

Man-made structures have the potential to negatively impact marine life through habitat displacement, pollution, and behavioural disturbances. However, they have also proven to benefit ecosystems through the addition of complex hard substrate which increases biodiversity and may provide greater foraging opportunities, as well as shelter from predators, in addition to shelter from fishing activities and shipping noise. While localised increases in productivity and abundance of fish have been recorded around turbines, there is not yet evidence of increased productivity at a regional scale from the expansion of OWFs in European waters.

Vessels, whether commercial, shipping, or recreational, may impact both marine mammals and fish through noise, localised chemical pollution from leaks and spillages, possibility of ship-strikes, and as vectors for invasive species. Impacts include disruption to functional behaviours such as resting, foraging, or communication. In general, marine mammal numbers decrease in response to increased vessel numbers, and vessels travelling at speed have greatest impact. Fish display lower anti-predator responses, or spend more time guarding nests than feeding in the presence of increased vessel activity, and few reports exist of fish being struck by vessels.

The potential impacts from cables include possible entanglement, localised changes in the electromagnetic field (likely negligible impact for marine mammals, local moderate impact for elasmobranchs and possibly some crustaceans), sediment suspension, noise/vibration, heat, and reef/reserve effects.

However, this stressor is poorly studied, and more research would provide greater clarity on several of these issues.

Impacts will be best mitigated by appropriate site selection and assessment of potential wind farm sites, using the best available data on species spatial and temporal distributions or conducting additional surveys where necessary. Additional mitigation measures including time-area restrictions, the controlled use of acoustic deterrence devices, and other noise mitigation devices should be implemented to reduce impacts from noise – most importantly pile driving, but also vessel and operations noise. An update of Irish guidelines for permitted anthropogenic noise emission levels would help to inform these measures. Where possible, if one option has been shown to have lower negative impact over another available option, the first should be selected. Future OWF developments should take the findings of this report in to consideration, and further research should be carried out to fill in the gaps in knowledge.

5 Work Package 5: Markets, infrastructures, storage and economic benefits

5.1 Markets report - Identification of new and Future Markets (Deliverable D5.1)

Prepared by: Nguyen Dinh

Reviewed by: Paul Leahy, Valerie Cummins, Eamon McKeogh

Executive Summary:

This report highlights the importance of hydrogen energy in Ireland. For the benefits of potential stakeholders, particularly EirWind industry partners, methods of hydrogen production, storage and transportation, including the present and the predicted costs, and a description of fuel cells are briefly reviewed and discussed. The discussion includes a concept of offshore platforms for hydrogen production from wind farms. The markets for hydrogen are first demonstrated by its supply and consumer chains and schematic and sectorial applications. A number of relevant reference case studies of hydrogen markets are reviewed including:

- (i) Present and future viability of renewable hydrogen produced from wind farms in Germany and Texas, USA,
- (ii) The green hydrogen economy in the Northern Netherlands,
- (iii) The H21 Leeds City Gate project studying technical and economic feasibility of converting the existing natural gas network in Leeds to 100% hydrogen, and
- (iv) A list of typical hydrogen-based vehicles and infrastructures in operation or under construction throughout the world.

The opportunities for new and future hydrogen markets in Ireland are finally discussed with respect to reduction of wind energy LCOE and dispatch-down and to transport, industry, residential and other sectors. Actions to accomplish the market push and pull effects that need to be taken as a first priority by both market stakeholders and regulatory bodies, are proposed. Hydrogen needs to be included in scenarios of Ireland's future energy and government policy. In order to push the market-push, government policy intervention is required to overcome major barriers to a hydrogen economy. That include policy and incentives for utilities to transition to hydrogen. After generating such initial push, a retrospective market pull across the hydrogen supply chain as certainty of a hydrogen economy should be established through regulatory business plans.

Introduction Brief URL: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Information-Brief-Introduction-to-hydrogen.pdf>

5.2 Cost/Benefit and Risk Analysis Report (Deliverable D5.2)

Prepared by: Jochelle Laguipo

Reviewed by: Paul Leahy, Nguyen Dinh, Eamon McKeogh and Industry partners.

Executive Summary:

This report presents the case for hydrogen as a means of energy storage for renewables such as offshore wind in “power-to-gas” systems. Recent major developments in other countries adopting this type of energy system show the technological capabilities readily available. Ireland, without such systems, ranks second-worst in the EU for lack of climate action. This is a result from lack of political backing i.e. implementing policies or incentives, rather than a technological deficit.

Development of a methodology for the cost benefit analysis for a hydrogen energy system is the focus of this report. Three different scenarios for such a power-to-gas system are created to break down this analysis for better understanding – namely:

1. Grid connected power-to-gas
2. Off grid power-to-gas
3. Hydrogen for mobility

Each system is modelled as a 500 MW capacity offshore wind farm with a 45% capacity factor. The chain of hydrogen production is broken down into the its different cost factors, namely the main components required e.g. electrolyzers, compressors, storage methods.

For scenario 1, an electrolysis plant of 11.25 MW capacity is possible with a total cost of €15 to €19 million. Using only dispatched-down wind, 1.2 tons per hour of hydrogen can be produced (during peak load). For scenarios 2 and 3, 50 to 60 tons of hydrogen per hour is possible assuming that load input is offshore wind farm’s full capacity. The total cost for this scenario is estimated to be €597 to €716 million.

The benefits for each scenario are more qualitative. Hydrogen offers a solution for decarbonization of various industries. The demand for hydrogen is increasing and there is a great economic opportunity for Ireland to become a “hydrogen valley” serving different industries. Failing to adapt such a system is a significant opportunity cost. Apart from avoiding a €600 million annual EU fine for failing to achieve 2020 renewable energy targets, potential significant reduction of CO₂ emissions cannot be quantified with a price tag as it is invaluable. Applications of hydrogen for different industries are discussed to support the advantages and benefits of hydrogen production. Action is recommended to remove policy and regulatory barriers in order to enable power-to-gas developments in Ireland.

5.3 Cost-Benefit Analysis of a large-scale power-to-hydrogen system integrated with offshore wind (Deliverable D5.2.2)

Prepared by: Jochelle Laguipo, Pedro Pereira

Reviewed by: Paul Leahy, Nguyen Dinh, Eamon McKeogh and Industry partners

Executive Summary:

The levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH₂) is the focus of this cost analysis. LCOH₂ measures the economic viability of an energy technology for commercialization. A large-scale power-to-gas system integrated with an offshore wind farm is considered. Capacities greater than 50 MW are considered large scale in this analysis. The initial capital costs increase linearly with scale however; it was found that above a certain threshold the LCOH₂ becomes independent of scale, as demonstrated in **Figure 5-1**. PEM electrolyzers have slightly lower LCOH₂ than alkaline electrolyzers. At a smaller scale, the LCOH₂ starts at €5.42 per kilogram, then decreases to €5.24 per kilogram after 20 MW and eventually remains at €5.17 per kilogram above 51 MW capacity. LCOH₂ is lower for longer system lifetimes. Electricity from offshore wind is the most significant contributor accounting for 67-70% of the LCOH₂. Lower electricity costs will significantly reduce the cost of hydrogen.

In Ireland, there are two likely target markets for hydrogen applications. The first is the decarbonisation of transport. Different scenarios are outlined in **Table 4** for decarbonising the road fleets and the annual CO₂ emissions avoided is calculated with the results in Error! Reference source not found.. The best-case scenario is decarbonising all road transport that avoids 1571 ktCO₂ emissions annually. Decarbonising public transport only will avoid 18 ktCO₂ annually. The latter would be a good starting point. However, a more ambitious scenario, Scenario 2, is presented where hydrogen is used to fuel heavy vehicles such as delivery trucks, public transport, state-owned vehicles e.g. ambulances or fire trucks, which would be a better starting point for decarbonising the transport sector, as it would ultimately deliver greater reductions in CO₂ emissions. Decarbonising the entire gas grid will avoid 9.49 Mt of CO₂ annually.

Figure 5-1: Levelised Cost of Hydrogen with increasing capacity of electrolyser plant

Table 4: Scenarios for application of hydrogen for decarbonisation in the transport sector

Scenario 1	All road vehicles
Scenario 2	This includes goods vehicles, tractors and machinery, public transport and exempt vehicles. Exempt vehicles are those exempted from liability to pay motor tax e.g. ambulances, fire trucks, state-owned vehicles (Kilkenny County Council, 2019).
Scenario 3	Private vehicles only – this includes private cars and motor cycles.
Scenario 4	50% of private vehicles (other 50% still use fossil fuels) and scenario 2.
Scenario 5	Public transport only

Figure 5-2: CO2 abatement for different road decarbonisation scenarios.

5.4 Infrastructure and Cost-Benefit Analysis for an Offshore Wind-to-Hydrogen System: Case Study 1 (Deliverable D5.3)

Prepared by: Jochelle Laguipo

Reviewed by: Paul Leahy, Nguyen Dinh, Eamon McKeogh

Executive Summary:

This report presents an infrastructure and cost-benefit analysis for a grid-connected power-to-hydrogen system that delivers hydrogen for transport applications. The infrastructure analysis identifies the necessary hydrogen infrastructure to be in place in order to facilitate the delivery of hydrogen along its value chain from hydrogen generation using offshore wind energy, via transmission to end-use applications in the transportation sector. There are different pathways for hydrogen depending on its end use applications. Each pathway will have incurred different costs due to difference in infrastructure required.

The cost analysis identifies the required initial investments and the levelized cost of hydrogen. It covers the projected revenue for the sale of hydrogen and the projected profits. This is based on the previous EirWind deliverable D5.2.2 - Cost-Benefit Analysis of a large-scale power-to-hydrogen system integrated with offshore wind.

Both analyses are applied to a theoretical case study: a grid-connected offshore wind farm coupled with a power-to-hydrogen system. The end use of the hydrogen output from the system is fuel for road transport. The LCOH₂ breakdown is presented in **Figure 5-3**. The largest proportion of the cost is associated with electricity purchase, therefore there may be opportunities to reduce costs by exploiting 'dispatched down' wind energy that would otherwise be lost, or to purchase energy on the balancing market. Other major costs are, in decreasing order: capital costs, compression costs and storage costs. The delivery cost is also included in this analysis but accounts only for 0.2% of the LCOH₂; hence making little to no change on the cost of hydrogen.

Having a clear hydrogen pathway incorporating economics, energy security and environmental sustainability is important for the beginning and future of hydrogen as an energy carrier. The ideal client candidates are public transport, fleet vehicles and delivery vans. Providing a supply of hydrogen can create its own demand, and as the demand grows, the infrastructure to generate and distribute hydrogen can grow organically. However, the introductory phase will require a collaborative effort between suppliers and end-user clients.

Figure 5-3: LCOH2 cost breakdown for a 200 MW PtH

5.5 Demonstration pilot design and recommendations for zero-emissions offshore wind support vessels (Deliverable D5.5)

Prepared by: Pedro Pereira

Reviewed by: Paul Leahy, Nguyen Dinh

Executive Summary:

Maritime activities represent more than 50% of the total lifetime cost of an offshore wind farm. In addition, traditional diesel engines and bunker fuels will struggle to meet stringent regulations coming into place in the near future. In this context, innovative solutions are required to increase system efficiencies, reduce fuel consumption and diminish emissions of vessels used in the offshore wind industry. Fuel cells stand out as a possible solution due to their potential for reducing emissions while presenting several other benefits. Thus, this report evaluates the suitability of fuel cells as the main power source for offshore wind support vessels, particularly Crew Transfer Vessels (CTVs) using pure hydrogen as fuel.

CTV's were considered for this study due their relevance in offshore wind farm operation and maintenance as they represent a proportion of 40.6% of the total number of vessels in the entire wind market. Regarding the governing factors of CTV designs, fuel cells have the potential to reduce fuel consumption, increase comfort for crew and technicians and reduce emissions. To power both propulsion and auxiliaries of hydrogen-fuelled CTV's, different fuel cell types were evaluated. LT-PEMFC are the most suitable fuel cell type to be used in hydrogen-fuelled CTVs due to having the highest volumetric and gravimetric densities amongst all fuel cells, good lifetime capabilities, excellent cold start times and load transient response. For on-board hydrogen storage, the current approaches include compressed gas, liquid hydrogen (LH2) and chemical storage (sorbents, metal hydrides and chemical hydrides). Because LH2 is the most compact and light technology to store hydrogen, this is the most promising method of storing hydrogen on CTVs.

Because LH2 is very similar in its physical and combustion properties to liquid natural gas (LNG) and since LNG ships are already being designed by naval architects, and approved by the international and domestic regulatory shipping authorities, both fuels were compared regarding safety. Overall, hydrogen is as safe as liquid natural gas (LNG) for use in gas-fuelled vessels and currently, there are no specific and comprehensive rules governing hydrogen installations on ships. The main regulations are the International Code of Safety for Ships using Gases or other Low-flashpoint Fuels (IGF code) and the DNV GL rules for gas fuelled vessels, however, they are primarily specific to natural gas applications.

The proposed possible future studies are: An economic analysis of fuel cell and hydrogen storage systems and also to survey/estimate the CTV demand in future markets and their hydrogen consumption; Address the operational issues of fuel cells in the maritime environment; Develop a case study to estimate weight and volume of the hydrogen storage and fuel cell systems; and assess the potential of ammonia.

6 Work Package 6: Synthesis

6.1 Literature and methodology for Synthesis /Blueprint of sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland (Deliverable D6.2)

Prepared by: Nguyen Dinh

Reviewed by: Val Cummins

Executive Summary:

This study aims to review relevant blueprints, visions and masterplans for offshore wind development in other countries, in order to inform a methodology for writing a blueprint, arising from the research conducted in the EirWind project. The EirWind Blueprint is envisaged as a synthesis of the studies conducted through EirWind, ultimately presented, such that policy makers may derive value for forward (master) planning purposes.

Three case studies have been selected to cover a range of issues, including infrastructure, government supports, innovation and public engagement, from New York and Virginia in the United States, and Taiwan. The blueprint process and resulting masterplan for New York consists of a comprehensive suite of actions for site selection, grid development, economic supports and stakeholder engagement. The vision for Virginia outlines infrastructure and geographical advantages, and the opportunity for Virginia to become a hub for the East Coast offshore wind supply chain.. The Taiwan government's promotion targets, strategies and incentives for offshore wind including the "Thousand Wind Turbines" project, Feed-in-Tariff, and incentives for demonstration projects have effectively supported the offshore wind industry in that country. The high demand for electricity and strong grid in New York and Taiwan, which can absorb the large scale offshore wind power, require less action for route to markets, wind dispatch down resolution and power to gas, than in Ireland

Following issues identified in the case studies, the recommended future scope of work for WP6 should includes national and international clusters for supply chain, region-based REFiT and incentives, routes to transport and heat markets and storage of hydrogen, and cumulative impact assessment.

Lessons learned indicate that consideration of spatial and temporal scales are essential in developing the blueprint for sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland. A three-dimensional template is therefore proposed for correlating and analysing the information from each work package in EirWind, as an approach to synthesising the research, and for the development of a blueprint as the final project output. It will loop over results and recommendations including wind resources, data, ports and logistics, stakeholder groups, and grid to populate the template. The approach will provide a whole of Ireland view, as well as a separate analysis for the East Coast, South Coast, and West Coast, integrated with the GIS datasets and maps. As a next step, development scenarios for an agreed timeline, for example in 2025, 2035 and 2050, should be discussed and agreed with the Consortium.

7 Publications

The information below includes publications arising directly from EirWind work packages, and from the collaboration of SFI-funded researchers with other research groups.

7.1 Peer-reviewed papers (Indexed by Scopus, SCI, SCIE or Web of Science)

(**Bold**: member of EirWind research team)

WP2: Data management for site evaluation

- **J. L. Peters, T. Remmers, A. J. Wheeler, J. Murphy, V. Cummins** (in review). A systematic review and meta-analysis of GIS use to reveal trends in offshore wind energy research and offer insights on best practices. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*.
- **J. L. Peters**, P. Dunlop, S. Benetti (in review). Sedimentary and foraminiferal records of Late Quaternary environmental change west of Ireland and implications for the last British-Irish Ice Sheet. *Journal of Quaternary Science*.
- **J. L. Peters**, T. A. Brennand (near submission). Palaeogeographic reconstruction and hydrology of glacial Lake Purcell during MIS 2 and its potential impact on the Channeled Scablands. Intended Journal: *Boreas*.
- **J. L. Peters**, S. Benetti, P. Dunlop (near submission). Biostratigraphic history of the last British-Irish Ice Sheet on the northern Porcupine Bank and Slyne Trough, west of Ireland. Intended Journal: *Marine Geology*.
- **R. O'Connell**, L. de Montera, **J. Peters**, S. Horion (near submission). An updated assessment of Ireland's wave energy resource using satellite data assimilation and a revised wave period ratio. Intended Journal: *Renewable Energy*.
- **J. L. Peters, T. Remmers, A. J. Wheeler, J. Murphy, V. Cummins** (in preparation). Quantifying the effects of parameter weightings on offshore wind farm site selections. Intended Journal: *Renewable Energy*.
- V.Q. Doan, **V.N. Dinh**, H. Kusaka, T.V. Du, A. Khan, N.D. Duc and T. Cong (2019). Usability and challenges of offshore wind energy in Vietnam revealed by the regional climate model simulation. *Scientific Online Letters on the Atmosphere (SOLA)*, 15, 113-118, DOI: 10.2151/sola.2019-021.
- **T. Remmers**, F. Cawkwell, C. Desmond, **J. Murphy**, E. Politi (2019). The potential of advanced scatterometer (ASCAT) 12.5 km coastal observations for offshore wind farm site selection in Irish waters. *Energies*, 12, 206. DOI:10.3390/en12020206.

WP3 Development Optimisation for Cost Reduction

- H.X. Nguyen, **V.N. Dinh** and B. Basu (2019). A comparison of Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamic simulation with exact results from nonlinear water wave model. *Ocean Systems Engineering (Submitted)*.

- **V.N. Dinh** and B. Basu (2019). Spatially-varying non-stationary seismic bedrock motions. *Congrès International de Géotechnique - Ouvrages – Structures* (Accepted). URL: <https://cigos2019.sciencesconf.org/>
- P. Plodpradit, **V.N. Dinh** and K.D. Kim (2019). Tripod-supported offshore wind turbines: Modal and coupled analysis and parametric study using X-SEA and FAST. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 7(6), 181, DOI: 10.3390/jmse7060181.
- P. Plodpradit, **V.N. Dinh** and K.D. Kim (2019). Coupled analysis of offshore wind turbine jacket structures with pile-soil-structure interaction using FAST v8 and X-SEA. *Applied Sciences, Special Issue "Offshore Wind Energy"*, 9(8), 1633, DOI: 10.3390/app9081633.
- K.D. Kim, S. Vachirapanyaku, P. Plodpradit, **V.N. Dinh** and J.H. Park (2019). Development of offshore structural analysis software X-SEA coupled with FAST. *Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering (OMAE)*, Glasgow, UK.
- **V.N. Dinh** and H.X. Nguyen (2018). Design of an offshore wind farm layout. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* 18, 233-238, Springer Nature, DOI: 10.1007/978-981-13-2306-5_31.
- H.X. Nguyen, B. Basu and **V.N. Dinh** (2018). Numerical investigation of wave-current interaction by using smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* 18, 312-318, Springer Nature, DOI: 10.1007/978-981-13-2306-5_43.

WP4 Governance and biological

- **S. Kandrot, V. Cummins, D. Jordan, J. Murphy** (in preparation). Employment impacts of offshore wind development for Ireland. Intended Journal: *Renewable Energy*.
- **M. Kamidelivand, S Kandrot, Y Cronin, J. Murphy, V. Cummins.** (tentative title) Social transition of offshore wind energy, the role of stakeholder engagement, socio-economic impacts and benefit sharing mechanisms- Lessons for Ireland. In preparation. Intended Journal: *Energy, Sustainability and Society*.
- **M. Kamidelivand, J. Murphy, V. Cummins.** (tentative title) Potential for the co-existence between fishers and offshore wind farm developers. Mitigation options and building trust. A case of Ireland. In preparation. Intended Journal: *Marine Policy*.
- G. Arneill, **E.J. Critchley**, S. Wischniewski, **M.J. Jessopp**, and J.L. Quinn (2019). Acoustic activity across a seabird colony reflects patterns of within-colony flight rather than the nest density. *IBIS* doi.org/10.1111/ibi.12740
- **E.J. Critchley**, W. J. Grecian, A. Bennison, A. Kane, S. Wischniewski, A. Cañadas, T.D. Tierney, J.L. Quinn and **M.J. Jessopp** (2019). Assessing the effectiveness of foraging radius models for seabird distributions using biotelemetry and survey data. *Ecography* (accepted) DOI:10.1111/ecog.00119.
- **E.J. Critchley**, A. Kane, **M.J. Jessopp** and J.L. Quinn. An updated oil vulnerability index for seabirds: a European case study. In preparation – intended journal is *Marine Pollution Bulletin*

WP5 Markets, infrastructures and economic benefits

- **J. Laguipo, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, P. Leahy, J. Murphy, V. Cummins** (2019). Levelized Cost of Hydrogen from Offshore Wind Energy in Ireland. In Preparation - Intended Journal: *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*.
- **P. H. Todesco Pereira, P. Leahy, E. McKeogh, V. N. Dinh, J. Murphy, V. Cummins** (2019). Fuel cells suitability for zero-emission hydrogen-fuelled Crew Transfer Vessels (CTV): Technology review and recommendations. Await industry partners' approval - Intended Journal: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*.
- **V.N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, P. Leahy, J. Murphy, V. Cummins**. Development of a viability assessment model for hydrogen production from dedicated offshore wind farms. In Preparation, to submit to *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*.
- **V.N. Dinh** (2019). Viability of hydrogen production from a dedicated offshore wind farm-underground storage in the Irish Sea in 2030. *IOP journal conference series: Materials Science and Engineering (Conditionally accepted with minor revision)*.

WP6 Synthesis

- **V.N. Dinh** and **E. McKeogh** (2018). Offshore Wind Energy: Technology Opportunities and Challenges. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* 18, 3-22, DOI: 10.1007/978-981-13-2306-5_1

7.2 Research Reports/Policy Briefs:

WP2: Data management for site evaluation

- J. Peters, V. Cummins, A. Wheeler (2019). Data Resources Assessment—Phase 1, *EirWind Project Deliverable D2.1 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- J. Peters, V. Cummins, A. Wheeler (2019). Policy Brief: Data for Irish Offshore Wind Energy. MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland. Available from: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Policy-Brief-%E2%80%93Data-for-Offshore-Wind-in-Ireland.pdf>
- J. Peters, V. N. Dinh, A. Wheeler (2019). Field Measurement Plan 1, *EirWind Project Deliverable D2.2 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- T. Remmers, J. Peters, V. N. Dinh, V. Cummins, A. Wheeler (2019). Data set release 1, *EirWind Project Deliverable D2.3 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- J. Peters (2018). AggreWind Research Survey Report. Marine Institute Report for the National Research Vessels Ship-Time Programme, Marine Institute, Oranmore, Ireland. Available at: http://marinegeology.ucc.ie/wp-content/uploads/sites/87/2018/12/CV18034_cruise_report.pdf

WP3 Development optimisation for Cost Reduction

- R. Chester, J. Murphy (2018). Initial Issues in the Development of Offshore Wind in Ireland *EirWind Project Deliverable D3.1 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.

WP4 Governance and biological

- Y.Cronin, V. Cummins (2018). Stakeholder Issues and Mapping, *EirWind Project Deliverable D4.1 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- Y.Cronin, V. Cummins (2018). Stakeholder Mapping Directory, *EirWind Project Deliverable D4.1*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- Y. Cronin, V. Cummins (2018). Recommended Innovation and Best Practice Stakeholder Engagement, *EirWind Project Deliverable D4.2 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- Y. Cronin, V. Cummins (2019). Stakeholder Perceptions Report – Part 1, *EirWind Project Deliverable D4.4 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- S. Kandrot (2019). Socio-economic modelling for the offshore wind sector in Ireland: A Review, *EirWind Internal Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- E.J. Critchley, V. Cummins and M.J. Jessopp (2019). Initial report on methodology for the assessment of seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland, *EirWind Project Deliverable D4.11 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- E.J. Critchley, V. Cummins and M.J. Jessopp (2019). Initial results for the assessment of seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland, *Deliverable D4.12 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- W. Hunt, E.J. Critchley, V. Cummins and M.J. Jessopp (2019). Impacts from Offshore Wind Farms on Marine Mammals and Fish – A review of the current knowledge, *Deliverable D4.13 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- E.J. Critchley, V. Cummins and M.J. Jessopp (2019). Assessing seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland, *EirWind Project Deliverable D4.11 Policy Brief*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.

WP5 Markets, infrastructures and economic benefits

- V. N. Dinh, P. Leahy, E. McKeogh and V. Cummins (2018). Deliverable D5.1 Markets report - Identification of new and Future Markets, *EirWind Project Internal Report*, MaREI Centre, ERI, UCC, November 2018.
- J. Laguipo, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, P. Leahy (2019). Cost Benefit and Risk Analysis, *Eirwind Project Deliverable D5.2 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- J. Laguipo, P. Pereira, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, P. Leahy (2019). Cost-Benefit Analysis of a Large-Scale Power-To-Hydrogen System Integrated With Offshore Wind, *Eirwind Project Deliverable D5.2.2 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.

- J. Laguipo, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, P. Leahy (2019). Infrastructure and Cost-Benefit Analysis for an Offshore Wind-to-Hydrogen System: Case Study 1, *Eirwind Project Deliverable D5.3 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- P. H. Todesco Pereira, V. N. Dinh, P. Leahy (2019). Demonstration pilot design and recommendations for zero-emissions offshore wind support vessels, *EirWind Project Deliverable D5.5 Report*, MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, Cork, Ireland.
- V. N. Dinh, J. Laguipo, P. Leahy and E. McKeogh (2019). Introduction to hydrogen. EirWind Project Information Brief. URL: www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Information-Brief-Introduction-to-hydrogen.pdf

WP6 Synthesis

- V. N. Dinh, J. Murphy, V. Cummins (2019). Synthesis /Blueprint development for phased approach to sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland. *EirWind Project Deliverable D6.1 report*, MaREI Centre. 2nd draft submitted for Consortium meeting on 27th August 2019.

7.3 Presentations/Talk/Conference chair/Facilitator (*: Speaker)

WP2: Data management for site evaluation

- J. Peters*, T. Remmers, A. Wheeler (2019). Work Package 2: Year 1 Review and Future Plans (Presentation). EirWind Consortium Meeting, Cork, 27 August 2019.
- J. Peters*, T. Remmers, A. Wheeler (2019). Data resource assessment for offshore wind development in Ireland—preliminary results and strategies for the future (Presentation). *Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org)* Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019, *EirWind Mini-symposium: Offshore wind in Ireland*, 60+ audience
- J. Peters*, T. Remmers, A. Wheeler (2019). Work Package 2: Field Measurement Plan (Presentation). EirWind Consortium Meeting, Cork, 2 May 2019.
- T. Remmers*, J. Peters, A. Wheeler (2019). Co-designing opportunities towards the development of Irish Offshore wind Energy (Presentation). *European Space Agency Living Planet Symposium*. Milan, 13 – 17 May 2019. 60+ audience
- J. Peters*, T. Remmers, A. Wheeler (2019). Work Package 2: Screening Report and Project Update (Presentation). Dublin, 31 January 2019.
- J. Peters*, T. Remmers, A. Wheeler (2018). Work Package 2: Data Management for site evaluation (Presentation). Ringaskiddy, 29 November 2018.
- J. Peters* (2018). Ireland's Offshore Quaternary Records (Session Chair). Irish Quaternary Association, Annual Symposium. Dublin, 23 November 2018.

WP3 Development optimisation for Cost Reduction

- F. Devoy McAuliffe*, J. Murphy (2019) WP3 Progress update (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 27 August 2019.

- V. N. Dinh*, K.D. Kim, P. Plodpradit, S. Vachirapanyakunb, J. H.Park (2019). Development of X-SEA program for efficient coupled analysis of offshore structure (Presentation), *Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org)* Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019, 20+ audience
- R. Chester, J. Murphy, V.N. Dinh* (2019). Initial Issues in the Development of Offshore Wind in Ireland (Presentation). *Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org)* Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019, *EirWind Mini-symposium: Offshore wind in Ireland*, 60+ audience
- K. D. Kim*, S. Vachirapanyaku, P. Plodpradit, V.N. Dinh and J.H. Park (2019). Development of offshore structural analysis software X-SEA coupled with FAST (Presentation). The 38th International Conference on Ocean, Offshore & Arctic Engineering (OMAE 2019), Glasgow, Scotland June 9–14, 2019. URL: <https://event.asme.org/Events/media/library/resources/omae/OMAE-2019-Program.pdf>
- P. Gade*, Jimmy Murphy (2019). O&M Expert (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Dublin, 31st January 2019.
- R. Chester*, J. Murphy (2018). Initial Issues in the development of Offshore Wind in Ireland. *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 29th November 2018.
- V.N. Dinh* and H.X. Nguyen (2018). Design of an offshore wind farm layout. *The First Vietnam Symposium on Advances in Offshore Engineering (VSOE, https://vsoe2018.sciencesconf.org/)*, Hanoi, 1-3 November 2018, 60+ audience.
- R. Chester*, J. Murphy (2018). WP3 Work plan. *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 30th August 2018.

WP4 Governance and biological

- S. Kandrot*, V. Cummins, D. Jordan (2019). Regional socioeconomic benefits and employment potential in the Irish offshore wind sector. *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 27 August 2019.
- S. Kandrot*, V. Cummins, D. Jordan (2019). Socioeconomic Study of Offshore Wind Development in Ireland (Presentation). *47th Regional Science Association International (RSAI) British and Irish Section Conference*, Cambridge UK, 18th July 2019.
- S. Kandrot*, Y. Cronin, M. Kamidelivand, E.J. Critchley, W. Hunt, D. Jordan, M.J. Jessopp, V. Cummins (2019). Social and biological considerations for offshore wind development in Ireland (Presentation). *Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org)* Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019, *EirWind Mini-symposium: Offshore wind in Ireland*, 60+ audience
- S. Kandrot*, V. Cummins, D. Jordan (2019). Socioeconomic Appraisal of Offshore Wind Development in Ireland (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 2 May 2019.
- S. Kandrot*, V. Cummins, D. Jordan (2019). Socioeconomic Appraisal of Offshore Wind Development in Ireland (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Dublin, 31 January 2019.
- Y.Cronin*, V. Cummins (2019). Work Package 4: Public Perception of Offshore Wind farms - Year 1 Review and Future Plans (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 27 August 2019.

- Y.Cronin*, V. Cummins (2019). Work Package 4: Public Perception of Offshore Wind farms – Progress (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 2 May 2019.
- Y. Cronin*, V. Cummins (2019). Understanding Public Perception of Offshore Wind Farms in Ireland (Poster). *Wind Europe Conference and Exhibition*. Bilbao, 02 – 04 April 2019. 60+ audience
- Y.Cronin*, V. Cummins (2019). Work Package 4: Public Perception of Offshore Wind farms - Progress (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Dublin, 31 January 2019.
- Y.Cronin*, V. Cummins (2019). Work Package 4: Public Perception of Offshore Wind farms – Literature Review and Methodology (Presentation). *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 29 November 2018.
- E. Critchley*, W. Hunt, M. Jessopp, V. Cummins (2019). Assessing the potential impacts of offshore wind on seabirds, marine mammals and fish – Annual review and work plan. *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 27 August 2019.
- E. Critchley*, W. Hunt, M. Jessopp, V. Cummins (2019). Assessing seabird vulnerability to offshore wind in Irish waters. *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 2 May 2019.
- W. Hunt*, E. Critchley, M. Jessopp, V. Cummins (2019). Environmental Impacts OWFs Marine Mammals. *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 2 May 2019.
- E. Critchley*, W. Hunt, M. Jessopp, V. Cummins (2019). Assessing the potential impacts of offshore wind on seabirds and marine mammals – Literature Review and Methodology. *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Dublin, 31 January 2019.

WP5 Markets, infrastructures and economic benefits

- P. H. Todesco Pereira*, J Laguipo, P. Leahy, V. N. Dinh (2019). Hydrogen consumption: Demonstration pilot design and recommendations for zero-emissions offshore wind support vessels (Presentation), *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 27 August 2019.
- J Laguipo*, P. H. Todesco Pereira, P Leahy, V. N. Dinh, E McKeogh (2019). Power-to-Hydrogen with Offshore wind (Presentation), *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 27 August 2019.
- V.N. Dinh* and V. Pushpoth (2019). Viability of hydrogen production from a dedicated offshore wind farm in the Irish Sea in 2030 (Presentation), *Energy Security and Chemical Engineering Congress* (ESChE, <https://esche.ump.edu.my/index.php/en/>), Penang, Malaysia, 17-19 July 2019, 40 audience.
- J Laguipo*, P Leahy, E McKeogh, V. N. Dinh (2019). Developing offshore wind to hydrogen infrastructure in Ireland - costs, benefits and risks (Presentation). *Wind Energy Science Conference* (WESC, www.wesc2019.org) Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019, EirWind Mini-symposium: Offshore wind in Ireland, 60+ audience
- V.N. Dinh* (2018). Hydrogen Production to Support the Development of Offshore Wind. *Irish Wind Energy Researchers Network Seminar* (Invited Presentation), Cork, 12 December 2018, 30* audience. URL: <https://community.ieawind.org/iwern/home>

- V.N. Dinh*, E. McKeogh, P. Leahy (2018). Can we amplify values of offshore wind in Ireland? (Invited Presentation). *Norwegian Offshore Wind Workshop Ireland*, Dublin, 4-5 December 2018. URL: <https://offshore-wind.no/event/workshop-ireland-2/>, 40+ audience.
- V. N. Dinh*, P. Leahy, E. McKeogh (2018). Identification of new and future markets (Presentation), *EirWind Consortium Meeting*, Cork, 29 November 2018.

WP6 Synthesis

- V. Cummins* (2019). The Role of Research and Innovation in building capacity for Blue Growth: The Eirwind Project (Invited Presentation). *Irish Marine Industry Showcase: Smart Maritime and Offshore Wind*, Cork, 11 June 2019. <https://www.ouroceanwealth.ie/oow-summit>
- V.N. Dinh* (2019). Experience in sustainable development of multi-sectors for offshore wind energy (Invited Presentation). *Offshore Wind Energy in Vietnam: Potential and Development Perspectives Workshop*, Vietnam-Japan Research Institute, Hanoi University of Science and Technology, 15 July 2019 (30 audience).
- V.N. Dinh* (2019). Technology solutions for offshore wind energy (Invited Presentation). *Offshore Wind Energy in Vietnam: Potential And Development Perspectives Workshop*, Vietnam-Japan Research Institute, Hanoi Univ. of Science & Tech, 15 July 2019 (30 audience).
- V.N. Dinh*, J. Murphy, V. Cummins (2019). Methodology for Blueprint of sustainable development of offshore wind in Ireland (Presentation). *Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org)* Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019, *EirWind Mini-symposium: Offshore wind in Ireland*, 60+ audience.
- V. Cummins* (2018). EirWind Project (Invited Presentation). *Norwegian Offshore Wind Workshop Ireland*, Dublin, 4-5 December 2018. URL: <https://offshore-wind.no/event/workshop-ireland-2/>, 60+ audience.
- V. N. Dinh* and E. McKeogh (2018). Offshore Wind Energy: Technology Opportunities and Challenges (Invited Keynote Presentation). *The First Vietnam Symposium on Advances in Offshore Engineering (VSOE, https://vsoe2018.sciencesconf.org/)*, Hanoi, 1-3 November 2018, 150+ audience.
- V. N. Dinh* (2018). Co-chaired the Plenary section (with Prof. Don DeGroot, University of Massachusetts Amherst, USA), *The First Vietnam Symposium on Advances in Offshore Engineering*, Hanoi, 1-3 November 2018, 300+ audience including attendance of H.E. Ms. Cáit Moran - Ambassador of Ireland to Vietnam, H.E. Dr Tran Hong Ha - Minister of Natural Resources and Environment of Vietnam and other two Vice Ministers.

8 Other Research Activities

The information below is focused on the added value initiatives undertaken by the researchers directly funded by SFI (not including the academic staff).

8.1 Editorial board/International Scientific Committee

- **S. Kandrot:** Co-editing Shorelines: The Coastal Atlas of Ireland (CUP Publication)
- **E.J. Critchley:** Member of an ICES (International Council for the Exploration of the Sea) advice drafting group on the environmental impacts of wet renewable technologies (March 2019)
- **V. N. Dinh:**
 - Member of International Scientific Committee, The 4th International Conference on Geotechnics for Sustainable Infrastructure Development (2019). <https://geotechn.vn/committees/#scientific-committee>
 - Co-Editor for Offshore Renewable Energy, with MF Randolph (The University of Western Australia), DH Doan (Subsea 7, France), AM Tang (Université Paris-Est, École des Ponts ParisTech), M Bui (GTC Lab, Dubai, UAE). Proceedings of the 1st Vietnam Symposium on Advances in Offshore Engineering, Springer Nature (2018).
 - Contribution to editing and review of MaREI Symposium (2018) Book of Abstracts published online: https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Book-of-Abstracts_MaREI-Symposium-2018.pdf

8.2 Examiner, Peer-reviewers for journal/conference papers

V.N. Dinh, peer-reviewer for:

- Energies, MDPI
- Environmental Earth Sciences, Springer
- IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology,
- International Conference on Geotechnics for Sustainable Infrastructure Development, Hanoi
- International Journal of GEOMATE, GEOMATE International Society
- International Journal of Steel Structures, Springer
- Journal of Structural Integrity and Maintenance, Taylor & Francis
- Smart Structures and Systems, Techno Press
- Structure and Infrastructure Engineering, Taylor & Francis
- Structural Control and Health Monitoring, Wiley & European Association for the Control of Structures.

J. L. Peters: Judged several research presentations at the 2019 Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC) in Cork, Ireland.

E.J. Critchley, peer-reviewer for:

- Animal Conservation and Wildlife Research

8.3 Research supervision (UCC students/internships)**V. N. Dinh**

- Supervised two M.Eng.Sc. Dissertations in Sustainable Energy at UCC:
 - Siddharth Joshi, “Opportunity identification of new energy market strategies for Ireland”. Achieved highest grade. Presently PhD Student in the MaREI Centre.
 - Vaishnav Pushpoth, “Local energy storage for offshore wind farms”. Presently engineer at Premium Power, Co. Dublin.

J. L. Peters

- Supervised an MSc student who completed an internship with the EirWind team as part of his research programme at The University of Copenhagen.
- Interviewed and helped select a new UCC MSc student (BEES School), now supervising this student (Evan O'Mahony).
- Helped establish a new research collaboration between MaREI and SEAI by working with GIS specialist Trevor Alcorn to adapt the general Opportunities and Constraints Model created for the Offshore Renewable Energy Steering Group for improved use with offshore wind developments. Maintaining this collaboration by keeping SEAI informed on progress with the model.
- Chief scientist on research cruise CV18034. This cruise was extremely successful, and the data generated is being used for EirWind research and for Evan O'Mahony's MSc research.
- Chief scientist on cruises CV19023 and CV19026, co-authored the grants that fund these cruises.

M. Kamidelivand

- Providing research assistance to Julia Miranda Machado, an Erasmus master student for a tentative research work on tourists perceptions of offshore wind development- cases of Ireland, Spain and Brazil.

J. Laguipo and P. Pereira

- Co-supervising an M.Eng.Sc. dissertation on “Converting surplus offshore wind-generated electricity to hydrogen” (Fionn Lyden), since September 2019.

8.4 Research Grant/Proposal**V. N. Dinh**

- Contributed to Offshore wind, Hydrodynamics, Numerical/Physical coupling, and Health monitoring sections, Science Plan of Mariner-i (Marine Renewable Energy Infrastructure).

- PI/partner applicant for two research proposals submitted to SEAI.
- Initialised contact with Mainstream Renewable Power (MRP) and secured MRP CEO's letter of support for future collaboration.
- Initialised contact and directly-raised EirWind fund from 3 industry partners (@€180,000). Co-initialised and co-raised EirWind fund (with PIs/Consultant) from other 6 industry partners (@€360,000).

J. L. Peters

- Helped co-author a successful iCrag research grant (Principal Investigator: Andrew Wheeler). The grant is titled: "Developing Offshore Wind Energy Seabed Zonation Tools (WindEaZ)."

9 Public Engagement

9.1 Voluntary work/ Support for public events

V.N. Dinh:

- Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org), Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019
- Member of Organising Committee, In-charge of Offshore Renew Energy group, MaREI Symposium, Cork, June 2018, <https://www.marei.ie/marei-symposium-2018/> . Contributed to organising (2 months) and chairing the ORE session at the Symposium.

J. L. Peters:

- Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org), Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019
- Our Ocean Wealth Summit (2019), Cork
- The INFOMAR (2018) Seminar, Kinsale

Y. Cronin:

- Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org), Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019
- Our Ocean Wealth Summit (2019), Cork

S. Kandrot:

- Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org) Cork, 17 - 20 June 2019
- Volunteer at MaREI stand at SeaFest, Cork, 9 June 2019
- Our Ocean Wealth Summit, Cork, 10 June 2019
- Helped organise and volunteered at MaREI for Ursulines School Trip, 3 May 2019

M. Kamidelivand:

- SeaFest (2019) Cork

- Our Ocean Wealth Summit (2019) Cork

E.J. Critchley:

- SeaFest stand for MaREI
- Presented at SoapBox Science in Cork (July 2019) on “Sharing the skies: can seabirds and offshore wind farms co-exist?” Good coverage on twitter for EirWind: <https://twitter.com/CullotyS/status/1147478816350253056>

J. Laguipo: Cork Discovers (27th September, 2019)

9.2 Project-related Twitter/LinkedIn/Social Media posts

- **V.N. Dinh:** Manage project LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eirwindproject/>
Number of project-related posts by the research team: 20+
- **V.N. Dinh:** <https://twitter.com/NDinh>. Number of project-related posts: 15+
- **J.L Peters:** Twitter account: @Jared_L_Peters; typically post ~4 tweets/month that focus on science and renewable energy; 101 followers.
- **J.L Peters:** Facebook account for science communication blog: @scienceosaurus; typically post ~4 tweets/month that focus on science and renewable energy; 292 followers. Page typically generates >200 engagements/week.
- **M. Kamidelivand:** Twitter: @Mitrakam, +50 tweets related to offshore wind
- **M. Kamidelivand:** <https://www.linkedin.com/in/mitra-kami-delivand/>, +9 posts in Eirwind LinkedIn.
- **E. J. Critchley:** <https://twitter.com/ejcritchley>, frequently posted.
- **Y. Cronin:** Created and managed the dissemination of Ireland first nation survey of public perception of offshore wind farms with over 1000 useable responses for further analysis with national representative and statistical robust (as parts of WP4 deliverables funded by EirWind).
- **S. Kandrot:** LinkedIn – occasionally share relevant posts
- **P. Leahy:** Shared information and made posts on wind energy and WESC, <https://twitter.com/uccwindenergy>

9.3 News/general articles/website/blogs

- **V. Cummins** (Interview), Irish Tech News, 17 June 2019. Presenting the EirWind Project at WESC 2019. URL: <https://irishtechnews.ie/presenting-the-eirwind-project-at-wesc-2019/>
- **V. Cummins** (Interview), *Irish Examiner*, 11 June 2019. Ireland emerging as attractive market for offshore wind. URL: <https://www.irishexaminer.com/breakingnews/ireland/ireland-emerging-as-attractive-market-for-offshore-wind-929987.html>

- **V. Cummins** (Interview), *The Independent*, 09 June 2019. Power giants in wind-to-hydrogen study. URL : <https://www.independent.ie/business/irish/power-giants-in-windtohydrogen-study-38194282.html>
- **J. Murphy** (Interview), *The Business Post*, 07 April 2019. Making waves in offshore wind energy. <https://www.businesspost.ie/focus-on/making-waves-offshore-wind-energy-440997>
- **D. Jordan**, *The Irish Examiner*, 04 February 2019. Offshore wind can blow many benefits our way. URL: <https://www.irishexaminer.com/breakingnews/business/offshore-wind-can-blow-many-benefits-our-way-902042.html>
- **VN Dinh**, *Irish Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade website*, 07 November 2018. Team Ireland attends the First Vietnam Symposium on Advances in Offshore Engineering.. <https://www.dfa.ie/irish-embassy/vietnam/news-and-events/news-archive/team-ireland-attends-the-first-vietnam-symposium-on-advances-in-offshore-engineering.html>
- **J. L. Peters**: Blogged for the Marine Institute’s Scientists@sea blog during the DOWindy research cruise (CV19023). <http://scientistsatsea.blogspot.com/?m=1>
- **J. L. Peters**: own and manage the science communication website <https://scienceosaurus.com/>. Over the past year, the site typically generated ~2,000 unique, unsolicited visitors/month, but periods with much more traffic are also common. Blog posts that drive the site’s traffic include:
 - “How to find scientific journal articles and avoid predatory or biased publications.” <https://scienceosaurus.com/how-to-find-scientific-journal-articles-and-avoid-predatory-or-biased-publications/>
 - “Why you should read scientific journal articles and 7 tips on how to do it.” <https://scienceosaurus.com/why-you-should-read-scientific-journal-articles-and-7-tips-on-how-to-do-it/>
 - “Climate-change news: diminishing Arctic sea ice may be more important than we thought.” <https://scienceosaurus.com/climate-change-news/>
 - “Anthropogenic climate change and ground water—we’re doing it wrong.” <https://scienceosaurus.com/anthropogenic-climate-change-ground-water/>

Appendix A: Galleries

Outreach Activities

Figure A-1: Some of the EirWind research team on the Naval ship LÉ George Bernard Shaw, Cork 10th June 2019.

Figure A-2: Dr Jimmy Murphy, EirWind Co-PI presented project updates to the Technical Advisors and chaired a Q&A session of industry partners, advisors and research team, Cork, August 30, 2018

Figure A-3: HE Mr Simon Coveney - Tánaiste (Deputy Prime Minister) and Minister for Foreign Affairs and Trade with EirWind industry partners at the EirWind Networking Event on June 10, 2019

Figure A-4: Vice Admiral Mark Mellett -Chief of Staff of the Irish Defence Forces speaking at the MaREI EirWind Networking Event on June 10, 2019.

Figure A-5: The Norwegian Ambassador to Ireland, Her Excellency Else Berit Eikeland (second from left) attended the MaREI EirWind Networking Event on June 10, 2019

Figure A-6: Dr Val Cummins - EirWind Co-PI introduced project consortium at the Irish Marine Industry Showcase in the Cork City Hall, June 11, 2019.

Figure A-7: Dr Paul Leahy - EirWind WP lead introduced the project and drivers at EirWind Mini-symposium: Offshore wind in Ireland, Wind Energy Science Conference (WESC, www.wesc2019.org), Cork, June 18, 2019.

Figure A-8: MaREI EirWind research team, industry partner representatives and technical advisors, in front of the Banking hall, UCC CUBS building, Lapps Quay, Cork, August 27, 2019.

Research

Figure A-9: EirWind Consortium meeting to review project technical progress and deliverables, Wilton Park House, Dublin 31st January 2019

Figure A-10: Recovery of the Shipek grab sampler south of Country Cork, Ireland. Sediment grabs are used to characterise the seabed's surficial sediment cover and ground-truth backscatter data

Figure A-11: Sediment samples (11-cm vibrocore sections) collected for aggregate potential mapping and the Eirwind project aboard the RV Celtic Voyager

Figure A-12: The 3-m vibrocorer used to collect Eirwind sediment cores on the deck of the RV Celtic Voyage

Planned and consented offshore wind farms in Ireland

Data source: 4C Offshore, DP Energy (Inis Ealga)
 Data Integrated: n/a
 Temporal Resolution: n/a
 Spatial Resolution: n/a
 Reference Methodology: n/a

Coordinate System
 Projection: Transverse Mercator
 Datum: IRENET95
 Date: 23/07/2019
 Author: Sarah Kandrot

Disclaimer

The content of the publication herein is the sole responsibility of the authors and does not necessarily represent the views of the industry partners, Science Foundation Ireland, University College Cork or their services. Without derogating from the generality of the foregoing neither the EirWind Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be liable for any direct or indirect or consequential loss or damage caused by or arising from any information advice or inaccuracy or omission herein.

Figure A-13: Planned and consented offshore wind farms in Ireland, by Sarah Kandrot

Appendix B: Proposals, Policy/Information Briefs, Responses to Consultation

EirWind Proposals & Workplan

- [1] V. Cummins, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, J. Murphy and A. Wheeler, “EirWind Full Proposal,” Submitted to MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy and Science Foundation Ireland, April 2018, 2018a.
- [2] V. Cummins, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, J. Murphy and A. Wheeler, “EirWind Workplan,” Submitted to MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, and Science Foundation Ireland, April 2018, Cork, 2018b.
- [3] V. Cummins, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, J. Murphy, A. Wheeler, P. Leahy and M. Jessopp, “EirWind Full Scope of Work,” MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, August 2018, Cork, 2018c.
- [4] V. Cummins, V. N. Dinh, E. McKeogh, J. Murphy, P. Leahy and M. Jessopp, “Clarifications on the Proposed Extended Scope of Work for Work Packages 4, 5 and 6,” MaREI Centre for Marine and Renewable Energy, September 2018, Cork, 2018d.

Policy Brief - Data for Irish Offshore Wind-Energy

- URL: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Policy-Brief—Data-for-Offshore-Wind-in-Ireland.pdf>
- Resulted from the Deliverable D2.1 - Data Resources Assessment—Phase 1 (Data Requirements, Gap analysis and Strategic Plan)

Policy Brief – Assessing seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland

- URL: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Policy-Brief-Assessing-seabird-vulnerability-to-offshore-wind-farms-in-Ireland.pdf>
- Resulted from the Deliverable 4.11 – Initial report on methodology for the assessment of seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms in Ireland.

Information Brief – Introduction to hydrogen

- URL: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Information-Brief-Introduction-to-hydrogen.pdf>
- Resulted from the deliverable D5.1 – Markets report-Identification of new and Future Markets

Response to Public Consultation on National Marine Planning Framework Baseline Report submitted to Ireland’s Department of Housing, Planning and Local Government (2018)

- URL: https://www.housing.gov.ie/sites/default/files/public-consultation/files/responses/110_eirwind.pdf

EirWind’s Grid & Marine Spatial Planning Workshop Public Report (2019):

- URL: <https://www.marei.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Public-Report-developed-from-EirWind’s-Grid-Marine-Spatial-Planning-Workshop.pdf>